

УДК 577.21:616.853-009.11-071

BIOINFORMATIC ANALYSIS OF MICRORNAS TARGETING THE SCN8A GENE IN EPILEPTIC ENCEPHALOPATHY

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Abstract. *In this study, an in silico analysis was conducted to identify potential microRNAs (miRNAs) regulating the expression of the SCN8A gene, which is associated with the development of SCN8A-related epileptic encephalopathy (SCN8A-DEE). The SCN8A gene encodes the Nav1.6 sodium channel, involved in the generation of nerve impulses. To identify possible regulators, the miRDB database—based on the MirTarget algorithm was used. The analysis identified hsa-miR-107, hsa-miR-103a-3p, hsa-miR-15b-5p, hsa-miR-16-5p, and others, suggesting their likely involvement in the regulation of SCN8A expression. The results indicate a potential role of these miRNAs in the post-transcriptional regulation of SCN8A and in the molecular mechanisms underlying the pathogenesis of SCN8A-DEE, making them promising therapeutic targets for correcting dysregulated sodium channel expression.*

Keywords: *SCN8A, microRNA, epilepsy, in silico analysis, SCN8A-DEE, miRDB.*

Epilepsy is a chronic neurological disorder characterized by recurrent seizures caused by abnormal neuronal excitability [1]. Genetic forms of epilepsy are often associated with mutations and disturbances in the post-transcriptional regulation of genes encoding ion channels. Among these, the *SCN8A* gene plays a crucial role, as it is highly expressed in the central nervous system and encodes the α -subunit of the sodium channel Nav1.6, which is involved in regulating excitatory neuronal networks [2]. Mutations in *SCN8A* lead to the development of early infantile epileptic encephalopathy type 13 (SCN8A-DEE), causing impaired inactivation and premature reopening of Nav1.6 channels, thereby increasing neuronal excitability.

In the present study, an in silico analysis was performed to identify potential miRNAs capable of regulating the expression of the *SCN8A* gene, using the miRDB database (<https://mirdb.org/cgi-bin/search.cgi>). miRDB is a bioinformatic database and analytical platform designed for predicting interactions between microRNAs and their potential target genes.

During the in silico analysis, a total of 320 potential microRNA candidates were identified as putatively interacting with the *SCN8A* gene, with predictive scores ranging from 50 to 100. Among them, the most probable regulators of *SCN8A* include hsa-miR-107, hsa-miR-103a-3p, hsa-miR-6867-5p, hsa-miR-5011-5p, hsa-miR-544a, and others, all exhibiting target scores between 98 and 100. This indicates a high likelihood that these miRNAs participate in the post-transcriptional regulation of Nav1.6 expression, thereby modulating neuronal network excitability. Thus, miRNA analysis provides valuable insights into the pathogenic mechanisms of SCN8A-DEE and helps identify potential therapeutic targets for correcting dysregulated sodium channel expression.

REFERENCES

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